

The Interior Design Proposals of Buildings for Tourism Purposes

Şebnem Ertaş

Abstract—“Architecture” is one component of sustainable cultural tourism. The sustainability of architecture is possible through preservation and restoration activities. In Turkey, which has an important place in the world’s cultural heritage, several studies focused on the sustainability of the cultural heritage were done in terms of the principles of “preserve-use-sustain”. Within the scope of this study, a methodology will be proposed in order to obtain the development of different scenarios supporting sustainable tourism. Sille is an ancient village located on the Spice Road and Silk Road dating back to the Ottoman and Seljuk eras. However, in recent years it is protected as an archeological site. In the “Alternative Project Phase”, the streets and buildings which bring dynamism to trade are determined; among these, 10 major buildings in Hacı Ali Ağa Street are studied.

Keywords—Tourism, cultural tourism, sustainability of architecture, interior design, Sille.

I. INTRODUCTION

TOURISM activities are experiencing rapid changes depending on ever-changing tourism expectations and needs within the globalizing world. Cultural tourism took its place in this process. Cultural tourism, which is fed by sustainable culture heritage sites, by its nature, is the most prevalent activity in tourism [1]. It is a kind of tourism activity in which the cultural values of a certain region are the main source of attraction. Tourist attractions which are considered within cultural tourism include all kinds of features and objects that are particular to a certain region such as artworks, handcrafts, traditional ways of living, tools the community use in their daily lives, religious beliefs, as well as the museums in which art works are exhibited and musical attractions such as opera and theatre [2]. The traditional texture and structural characteristics of a certain region play an effective role in the development of cultural tourism.

The following facts, which are; the architectural texture of buildings undergo change over time, along with their relation to people and nature; and buildings constitute a cultural accumulation belonging to their region; and the physical features of buildings are longer-lasting than their original functions, present the obligation of rearrangement according to today’s and future’s conditions [3].

When structurally standing buildings converted into a state in which they fail to fulfill the function for which they were intended, a re-evaluation of the structures ability to fulfill different functions which are appropriate for the current time seems inevitable. Thereby, their historical continuity can carry

on; and economic benefits can be provided by reducing their probable harm towards nature [4].

A significant change has been observed in tourism consumption patterns in recent years, parallel to the fast-paced global economic, political, and technological development. Tourism, which contributed significantly to the country’s economy, especially after 1980, has now become one of the most important sectors contributing some 15% to 20% to foreign trade and enabling a high level of foreign currency flow into the country. The statement: “a Master Plan will be prepared with the aim of providing a healthy and long-range development of the tourism sector”, which is mentioned the Turkey - Tourism Strategy 2023 - 9th Development Plan, intends to increase the country’s revenue share from tourism by developing tourism alternatives within the balance of “protect & use & sustain” for the natural, cultural, and historical values of the country [5].

In Turkey, which possesses a remarkable share of the world’s cultural heritage, it is necessary to rearrange approaches and applications of cultural entities. Although, cultural heritage is entering into a process of a rapid extinction and cannot be evaluated as it is supposed to be, certain practices within the protect-use-sustain principle for cultural heritages began to be applied [6]. The following projects are among these practices: Safranbolu (Karabuk), Beypazarı (Ankara), Cumalıkızık (Bursa), Odunpazarı (Eskişehir), Hamamönü (Ankara). However, in these projects, facade works are given importance, while the organization of interior space becomes insufficient due to erroneous and inadequate functional set-ups. Having raised this insufficiency, it was seen that the development of alternative projects with the aim of both functional set-ups and accurate interior-space organization can be tried. For this reason, the necessity for new functional suggestions and space solutions for the same buildings emerged. In this way, the most accurate function among the proposals put forward can be evaluated on the basis of city, street and structure, and can be handled as a whole in regards to sustainable tourism.

In this study, the stage of producing alternative projects, which encompass the preliminary investigation for the stage of preparing interior space projects within the scope of project 4 class executed by the interior-architecture lecturers of Karadeniz Technical University conducted on Konya/Sille, which has an important historical texture. Konya/Sille is seen as the most appropriate settlement for this stage, both for its cultural and historical values, and also due to the support of Konya Municipality, Konya Regional Conservation Council and the public. With the aim of supporting cultural tourism, 10

Ş. Ertaş is with the Department of Interior Architecture, Karadeniz Technical University, Trabzon, Turkey (e-mail: sebnemarc@hotmail.com).

residences were chosen as the pilot area for re-functioning in Hacı Ali Ağa street, where the residential texture is intense.

II. KONYA- SILLE/HACI ALI AĞA STREET

Konya, which has huge tourism potential, plays a significant role in regards to alternative tourism, in addition to religious tourism and alternative tourism. In this context, “Konya’s tourism map”, which presents Konya’s potential for cultural, cave, health, hunting and congress tourism, was generated. The map highlights the tourism potential for the counties displayed to open new tourism corridors outside the Konya city center. Sille is one of the corridors suggested for cultural tourism [7].

Sille has a quality of maintainability, as it is very close to Konya province, and it protects its natural and cultural values to a great extent. It is a place that has different features with its geographical structure, ecological features (in the past Greek and today only Turkish), socio-cultural structure, lifestyle, belief and traditions [4]. Thus, it became a tourist attraction for both national and international tourists for its cultural values (Aya Eleni and Cave churches, mosques, fountains,

baths, buildings, etc.), thanks to the restoration works of the Selçuk Municipality, which supports cultural tourism.

Sille is one of the most significant population centers of Anatolia, with its history and culture dating back to very ancient times. It was a number of civilizations and harbored many different cultures for many years. For this reason, it gains further importance for its sentimental values, in addition to its buildings which bear traces of those different cultures. Sille is one of those rare places that have enabled different beliefs and cultures to live and thrive in the same geography, and for this reason it is also called as the valley of culture [8]. Sille’s residential area, which is situated on the ancient Silk and Spice routes and seen as an important historical trade center, presents a highly sophisticated view in terms of cultural values with its mosques, churches, streets, fountains, and traditional houses in the cubic architectural style integrated by stoops and flat roofs. Sille, situated 8 km northwest of Konya, is a unique residential center for its culture, lifestyle, topography, customs and beliefs, in which both the Muslim and Non-Muslim population live together (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Konya- Sille

The pre-Republican era has the characteristics of a socially, culturally, economically and municipally developed city, with a population of 18,000 (including surrounding villages connected to the Sille Municipality). During that era much of the population was comprised of Greeks. Later, the Non-Muslim population was sent to Greece as the result of the decisions in the Republican Era [9]. After the forced population exchange of the Greeks, who dominated the economic and commercial life of Sille, the city experienced a major upheaval and sudden deterioration, losing its dynamism in terms of its economic, social, and cultural life; it gained the image of a deserted city. Despite losing its previous liveliness, Sille continues to project the appearance of an ancient city (Fig. 2). Carpet weaving, which is a source of income for the local population and whose reputation is internationally recognized, continues; although production has declined.

Besides, Central Anatolia’s only wax factory is also situated in this town and remains as a source of local employment. Agricultural activities, including vineyards and orchards, continue in the region; although these activities have also declined. Famous Sille grapes are still prevalent today. These various cultural factors give rise to the possibility of the development of alternative tourism, which can be understood by the ever increasing number of domestic and foreign tourists visiting Sille during tourism season [10].

Fig. 2 Sille [11]

The positive reactions encountered during the protection application process and construction plan implementation in 2001 to develop Sille as a tourism and recreational center, led to a touristic and recreational movement in Sille. Restoration works began, but failed to reach to their intended level in terms of interior spaces, since they only addressed exterior works. Particularly, original floor plans and features have been altered through irrational interventions to the interior spaces by their current inhabitants. For these reasons, Hacı Ali Ağa Street, which opens to the square having a dense residential texture, was chosen as a pilot study area for the project. Ten residences designated in tourism efficient Hacı Ali Ağa Street (Fig. 3). Along with the studies conducted on the plan basis of these houses, it is seen that a majority of the houses are two story or three story, and they stand out as a diversification of plan schema with a middle hall. The gall is united with a front roof or a balcony or a terrace. On the ground floor, a barn consisting of a stable, hayloft, stock room and serving spaces are situated; generally, this space has stone floor. The living area, which consists of sitting-rooms and bedrooms, are found upstairs. The incline of the land has meant that in some of the houses, alternative entrance doors are constructed for this level. The bathroom, toilet, and kitchen are located at the stair landing, which are generally made of wood. Besides, in the rooms of some houses, bathing cubicles are also constructed.

Attached buildings numbered one, two, three, and four overlook the square, being located the underside of the road. Because of the fact that between the houses three and four there is a newly-built reinforced concrete building, this building is excluded from the scope of study. The entrance of the houses numbered one and three are by the side of the square while the entrance of the house numbered two is from Hacı Ali Ağa Street. As for the house numbered four, it has two accesses; one is from square and the other one is from street. The houses numbered five, six, seven, eight, nine, and 10 are located on the upper part of the street in an attached way and their entrances open to the street. The house numbered five is located on a blind alley. The new rooms were added by closing wood girders due to increasing household population and the insufficient space. These kinds of newly created spaces are called "Hanay" and frequently used as the bedroom for the bride of the house. In addition, the houses numbered seven, eight, nine, and 10 have back yards by the level of the first and second story due to the inclination of the field. The house numbered six have a stony ground and

the living room that can be reached by two steps is used as a guest-room for the short visits of guests since it can be accessed easily [4].

Fig. 3 10 Houses determined as the working area

A. Refunctioning of the Buildings in Hacı Ali Ağa Street for Tourism Purposes

Sille, with its unique features, is a settlement whose sustainability should be provided. However, in terms of changing needs over time, the necessity of rearrangement and renovation of urban spaces (streets, squares, green areas) arose. In this context, Sille is a settlement that can be reevaluated in the scope of ecological design with its land use, settlement texture, open-green zones, buildings (with its construction form, crust and material), and economy and cultural life [11]. In this study, alternative projects constituting preliminary research for the preparation phase of interior space projects with the aim of Re-Functioning of the Buildings at Hacı Ali Ağa Street for Touristic Purposes. The "Alternative project production" stage, which consists of two different street suggestions based on different perspectives by producing two different suggestions for each construction, has

an important data quality for application projects; which is next stage.

The study consists of five steps with the aim of preparing alternative projects (Fig. 4);

1. Step: Creating the Working Team
2. Step: Literature Research and Inventory Works
 - Detection of Cultural and Historical Resource Values
 - Detection of Touristic Resource Values
3. Step: Field Analysis
 - Determining the Working Area
 - Status Analysis of Current Buildings
 - Functional Distribution Analysis for Each Building
4. Step: Formation Stage of Physical Renovation Projects
5. Step: Presentation of Different Alternative Projects

1. Creating the Working Team

The working team comprised of 39 students studying in the fourth semester of Karadeniz Technical University, Department of Interior Architecture; and the expert group comprised of three lecturers and one research assistant. Students take part in the study as a participant group with the purpose of producing different opinions by splitting into smaller groups. Each group of students is led by a member from the expert group. Apart from that, after interviewing with Selçuklu Municipality, who is an important participant, the areas requiring attention are determined in Sille. Face to face interviews were done with both Sille local and also with the land lords. In this way, different perspectives were tried to be created by the expert group via producing two different proposals for each building.

2. Literature Research and Inventory Works

In this step, it is aimed to reach all kind of publications on history, cultural and architectural structure of Konya-Sille. Physical renovation works with touristic purposes in the World and in Turkey will be analyzed.

3. Field Analysis

Current state of field will be analyzed as it is done at all physical renovation studies. Within this context, field analysis will be done in three stages.

- Determining the Working Area,
- Status Analysis of Current Buildings,
- Functional Distribution Analysis for Each Building.

The status analyses of the current buildings were carried out and their surveying determined the working area. The buildings were examined in terms of the construction technique and materials. Thereby, it was intended to put forward both exterior mass and also characteristic features of interior space.

4. Formation Stage of Physical Renovation Projects

Depending on the face to face interviews and area analyses, a re-functioning of the buildings in the determined area was carried out. Bringing liveliness to Sille for touristic purposes was the primary objective of the re-functioning.

5. Presentation of Different Alternative Projects

- Physical renovation project suggestions belonging to two different working groups, prepared as 1/50 model (street scale) and project (plan and section).
- By discussing the surveys and findings, the applicability of the study, which was carried out in a small part of the town, to the whole town of Sille will be emphasized.

B. Alternative Project Examples of the Buildings at Sille, Hacı Ali Ağa Street

At Hacı Ali Ağa Street, a function distribution analysis was prepared for each building by the working teams, in order to re-functionalize 10 houses by considering their architectural features, locations, and square meters. Each group created alternatives for the physical renovation projects based on these analyses. In this way, the most appropriate function identified by finding the solution of different function suggestions for the buildings.

Functions that will be employed to the current buildings are as:

- Accommodation (Boutique Hotel),
- Food and drink units (Cafe-Restaurant),
- Museum (Cultural facilities),
- Shopping area (Herbalist, Chandlery etc...),
- Carpet atelier.

In this context, both functional set-ups and space solutions of alternative projects are suggested as in Table I.

III. RESULTS

Tourism is one of the fastest developing industries of our age. This fast development provides the diversification of tourism products and places [12]. Protecting traditional and authentic values is among the principles of tourism. The positive process encountered during the preservation application with the construction plan approved in 2001 aiming to develop Sille as an attraction center in terms of tourism and recreation led to touristic and recreational activation in Sille; and afterwards restoration works started, yet these works stayed at exterior levels and cannot be reached to the intended level in terms of interior design. Particularly, the interior designs of the residences unconsciously interfered by their dwellers and so the residences moved away from their original set-up plans.

By providing accurate identification of the privileges which makes a place different than others, and by making an accurate planning about how they can be benefited with this proposed study, physical renewal projects consisting of different scenarios prepared for the preparation stage. While these projects were being carried out, different alternative functions were given to the buildings situated on the street. By presenting various examples for the chosen area, it was thought that different perspectives can be gained for the related institutions and organizations and for the social and economic actors/shareholders of the city. Thus, the field study handled with the approach sets an example for these kind of interior design projects to be applied to entire Sille Residential Area.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Sille, whose past dates back centuries to ancient times and known as an important center until the end of 19th century, can be transformed into an important central/historical attraction for Konya Province and an alternative tourism area through the right interior space renewal projects. In this way, its reputation both nationally and internationally can be raised with the aim of developing cultural tourism by opening tourism corridors in Konya province, which is at the center of tourism in Central Anatolia. The other aspect of this study is the positive contribution it will give to architecture and interior architecture of our country's Faculties of Architecture. For this purpose, it ensures the possibility for students to provide permanent solutions to the economical, physical, social and environmental conditions of the area by experiencing the texture and reality on site in a cooperative and coordinated way.

Within this context, the results presented for the working areas which are going to be project, follows:

1. Protecting the historical and natural heritage and gaining different perspectives to evaluate this heritage,

2. Diversifying tourism and popularizing cultural tourism,
3. Recovering the deserted buildings with hotel, cafe, restaurant, etc. functions,
4. Regenerating local handcrafts that are facing extinction for touristic purposes,
5. Providing income to the local economy through the new ateliers that are to be established,
6. Increasing the number of tourists and their average duration of stay,
7. Creating small and medium sized touristic facilities, reviving the handcrafts that are peculiar to the region (carpet, rug) and small businesses (candle work, pottery...) by building a tourism substructure,
8. Increasing the awareness of the natural, historical, cultural and semantic values of the region.

Fig. 4 The aim of preparing alternative projects

TABLE I
 SPACE SOLUTIONS OF ALTERNATIVE PROJECTS

		No.1	1. Suggestions / Cafe-Carpet Atcher		2. Suggestions /Cafe	
Facade						
Interior						
		No.2	1. Suggestions / Cafe		2. Suggestions/ Cafe	
Facade						
Interior						
		No.3	1. Suggestions / Hostel		2. Suggestions /Herbalist	
Facade						
Interior						

No.4		1. Suggestions / Boutique Hotel		2. Suggestions/ Boutique Hotel	
Facade					
Interior					
No.5		1. Suggestions / Restaurant		2. Suggestions/ Boutique Hotel	
Facade					
Interior					
No.6		1. Suggestions / Restaurant		2. Suggestions/ Cultural Museum	
Facade					
Interior					

No.7		1. Suggestions / Boutique Hotel			2. Suggestions/ Boutique Hotel		
Facade							
Interior							
No.8		1. Suggestions / Boutique Hotel			2. Suggestions/ Boutique Hotel		
Facade							
Interior							
No.9		1. Suggestions / Cafe			2. Suggestions/ Costume Museum-Cafe		
Facade							
Interior							

No.10	1. Suggestions / Honeymoon Hotel	2. Suggestions/ Restaurant
<p>Plan</p>		
<p>Section</p>		

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